

USING SONGS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: Songs play an important role in the development of young children learning a foreign language. The article deals with the use of songs in classes with preschool children in order to form an interest in the English language.

Key words: songs, authentic material, aesthetic education, music.

Teaching children a foreign language with the help of songs is an effective method of developing listening comprehension, pronunciation, strengthening grammatical structures, and most importantly, it is an excellent way to expand vocabulary. It has been proven that music has an effect on the right hemisphere of the brain, and speech on the left, which is why the rhymes of the text and pleasant music remain in our memory for a long time. In addition, songs evoke positive emotions, contribute to the development of memory and interest in learning English.

Some tips for using the song in class.

Firstly, the technique of using a song provides for the preliminary introduction and consolidation of lexical material, as well as grammatical structures of the song used. Also, don't forget to repeat the song in subsequent lessons. This will help the child to learn it well and for a long time. It is also necessary to understand that not every song is suitable for learning English with its help. It should be simple, with clear and repetitive phrases. You should not put the child on a song that is too fast, because he will not be able to keep up with repeating the words.

Currently, aesthetic education plays a special role. To resolve this issue, in addition to the principle of scientificity, it is also necessary to provide for a second equivalent principle of general pedagogy - artistry. Then there is a way of mastering the content through experiences, emotions, feelings. This is especially important for

preschool children in English classes. One of the most effective ways to influence the emotions and feelings of preschoolers is music. Music is part of the culture every people. Listening to the music of a certain people, you can get to know the culture, way of life, people, their worldview, traditions more deeply.

The famous Czech humanist teacher J. A. Komensky noted in his works that one who does not know music is likened to one who does not know the letter. According to the Soviet psychologist V. L. Levi, “music is one of the most effective ways to influence feelings and emotions..., which is the strongest psychological stimulus that penetrates into the hidden depths of consciousness”.

Any piece of music evokes certain emotions. The world of emotions is vast. Complexes of emotions appear in various combinations, which is why they are boundless. Music has an impact on personality education through the following forms of musical activity listening to music;

- creative activity, performance;
- cognitive activity;
- socially useful activity, manifested in conscious and active promotion of musical art.

Singing, being a means of expressiveness of music, helps to conduct a lesson with preschool children in a more enthusiastic and exciting way.

In English classes, songs are used to introduce and consolidation of new lexical material. This introduces an element of the game into the lesson and helps the teacher to organize a pause in the lesson in an interesting way. Children are very sensitive and receptive to emotional melody and therefore the song helps in productive memorization.

The song as a didactic material has a number of advantages:

1. accessibility through the Internet;
2. a huge amount and variety of language material;
3. Stable material update;

4. belonging to the culture of the country - additional linguistic and cultural information;
5. the presence of numerous and diverse registers of the language.

An analysis of the literature on this issue showed that in a foreign language lesson with preschool children, song material is used by teachers:

1. for greeting and farewell;
2. for phonetic drill;
3. for stronger consolidation of lexical and grammatical material;
4. as a stimulus for the development of speech skills and abilities;
5. as a kind of relaxation in the middle or at the end of the lesson when the children tired.

When choosing authentic song materials, careful selection is required based on the following principles:

- the principle of relevance;
- the principle of taking into account age characteristics;
- the principle of linguistic value;
- the principle of linguistic and cultural value;
- the principle of informativity.

The song can act as an incentive to study a foreign language subject.

It is important to create the right motivation and set up students positively.

Preschool children love to sing, dance and play. For them these activities are natural ways and means of knowing the world around us. We would like to tell you how we work with a song with preschool children. We listen to songs in which vocabulary is practiced through movements, gestures, facial expressions.

Work in English classes with preschool children is built as follows:

1. First, the song is listened to for the first time using visual material (pictures, diagrams).
2. Then the song is practiced a second time, accompanied by movements and dances.
3. Next, individual words and expressions from the song are analyzed.

4. The final playback of the song and its further use in the classroom.

Thus, from the point of view of the technique, the song in English can be considered, on the one hand, as an example of a sounding foreign language speech, on the other hand, being a carrier of cultural information, the song can also form the spiritual culture of the children, unite the soul and mind into a single whole. Song in the classroom with preschool children age gives impetus to children's creativity, and its use in the classroom in English enriches learners knowledge of a country-specific nature, students have an interest in the culture of the country of the studied language, and to the language itself.

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